

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF GENDER RELATED WORDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Komilova, Nilufar Abdilkadimovna

Lecturer, Fergana State University, Uzbekistan

Annotation: In this article, the lexical expressions of gender in English are investigated, the reasons for maintaining gender inequality in the language are shown and the level of the use of feminine terms is theoretically analyzed.

Keywords: English language, gender, gender indicators, lexeme, lexical layer, national features, gender category.

INTRODUCTION

In English, the gender category is less important than in other languages. The gender category is manifested in the gender of the referent and the alignment of objects with pronouns.

"These are, first of all, personal pronouns (he, she, it), possessive (his, her, its) and self (himself, herself, itself) pronouns or their substitutes, which correspond to the gender of living beings, or pronouns indicating inanimate objects. Accordingly, the concept of "natural gender" is superior to its formal expression, that is, "not only the words themselves, but also the objects expressed by these words are classified in the gender" [7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In modern English, the gender indicator is mainly found in nouns, especially feminine nouns, which are mainly derived from masculine words. Masculine nouns, on the other hand, are only considered gendered words in some cases, because they are mostly taken as generic words. Therefore, it can be said that "feminine root nouns perform an incomparably important task of preserving the root in the language compared to masculine root nouns" [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In English, gender-indicative nouns are formed in three different ways:

- 1) affixation (teacher - teacheress);
- 2) lexical expression (boy/girl);
- 3) adaptation by forming a syntactic combination (male nurse, he dog).

Lexical pairs with a gender indicator are mainly family relationships (father - mother, uncle - aunt, daughter - son, etc.), social roles (king - queen, lord - lady, etc.) and animals (bul - cow, cock - hen and etc.) are reflected in the names. Differences between femininity and masculinity can also be expressed through formal indicators that are syntactically linked:

Prepositive gender indicators: female officer, Mr. John, Miss Thorburn, lady doctor, girl graduate, male nurse.

Compound words with a gender indicative element: an Englishman, a Scotsman.

Derivative gender indicators: Actress Julia.

Derivative gender indicative words formed by personal pronouns: he lion, she lion, he - goat, she - goat [3].

Inflection - ess is definitely a feminine indicator, but -or/-er is not always considered a masculine indicator. Because - or/-er has a general meaning and is indicative of the masculine gender from which the feminine gender is formed, as cited in Longman Grammar of Spoken and Written English (2004).

The frequency of words ending with - man and -woman is 620/4 per one million words [1].

This indicators explain that most people are tend to use words ending with -man/-woman rarely. For instance, instead of using *salesman* or *saleswoman* they are preferring the lexeme *salesperson*. However, nearly all woman-form words have a man-form pair, and man-form words are often used generically.

Also, the dictionary lists words with the suffix -man that do not have the -woman form: *airman*, *alderman*, *ambulanceman*, *anchorman*, *barman*, *boatman*, *cabman*, *cameraman*, *churchman*, *clergyman*, *coalman*, *conman*, *countryman*,

craftsman. According to the dictionary, it was found that only *seamstress* does not have a masculine form among the words with -ess form [1].

The given data shows the linguistic reflection of gender differences existing in the society. Men still have power and authority. L. Push explains the reasons for gender inequality in the language as follows:

1. In most cases, society prefers to use nouns belonging to the masculine gender in a general sense.

2. Masculine terms have a dual function, that is, they can be applied to both women and men. If there is no indication of the gender of the referent, the term masculine is used.

During our analysis, it was also found that the words *madwoman* (*mad woman*) or *housewife* do not have a man-form pair. Furthermore, when comparing words presented as a feminine/masculine pair, it was observed that feminine terms do not have the same social equity power as masculine ones.

When referring to nouns representing the secondary (general) gender, (friend, individual, student) we use one or another pronoun according to the gender of the referent (he, his/she, her). However, when the gender of the referent is unknown, masculine pronouns are usually used.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the analysis of the lexical expression of gender confirmed the idea that most of the feminine gender nouns are derived from masculine gender nouns and allowed to observe another form of linguistic anthropocentrism.

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